

Attitudes toward service robots: Analyses of explicit and implicit attitudes based on anthropomorphism and construal level theory

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Purpose: Building on both the uncanny valley and construal level theories, the analyses detailed in this article address customers' explicit and implicit attitudes toward various service robots, categorized by the degree of their human-like appearance: mechanoids (low human-likeness), humanoids (medium human-likeness), and realistic robots (high human-likeness).

Methodology: The analyses reflect a mixed-method approach, across three studies. A qualitative study employs focus groups to identify consensual attitudes. An experiment measures self-reported, explicit attitudes toward the three categories of robots. Another experiment explores customers' implicit attitudes (unconscious and unintentional) toward robots, using three Implicit Association Tests.

Findings: Customers express both positive and negative attitudes toward service robots. The realistic robots lead to both explicit and implicit negative attitudes, suggesting that customers tend to reject these robots in frontline service settings. Robots with lower human-likeness levels generate relatively more positive attitudes and are accepted to nearly the same extent as human employees in hospitality and tourism contexts.

Originality: The combined qualitative and quantitative studies specify and clarify customers' implicit and explicit attitudes toward robots with different levels of human-likeness, in the real-world setting of hospitality and tourism services. Such insights can inform continued research into the effects of these service innovations.

Practical implications: Because customers reject, both consciously and unconsciously, very human-like robots in service encounters, managers should leverage this key finding, along with the more detailed results, to inform their strategic introduction of robots into hospitality frontline service settings.

Keywords: robot, artificial intelligence, explicit attitudes, implicit attitudes, human-likeness, construal level theory.

Paper type: Research paper

1. Introduction

By installing service robots, hotels and restaurants might attain substantial efficiency and productivity gains, especially if they can leverage such technology to perform repetitive tasks or cover challenging working hours (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a; Mariani and Borghi, 2021; Xu *et al.*, 2020). Their promise and appeal appears even greater during the COVID-19 pandemic, due to their capacity to offer contactless services (Jiang and Wen, 2020). Sales of service robots already increased 32% in 2020 (International Federation of Robotics, 2020), and the Spanish Association of Hotel Managers predicts they will perform 96% of hotel reception tasks and 42% of food and drink delivery in hotels within the next decade (Belanche *et al.*, 2020b).

Yet the emergence of service robots as a new type, or social category, of frontline agents also creates novel challenges for customers, who increasingly encounter these disruptive innovations (Belanche *et al.*, 2020c; van Doorn *et al.*, 2017). Unlike industrial robots, service robots can succeed only if customers accept them (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a; Kazandzhieva and Filipova, 2019), suggesting the pressing need for research that can predict and define customers' reactions to robot agents. Existing efforts along these lines, especially in the hospitality industry, tend to be theoretical, and they rarely address customer perspectives (Ivanov *et al.*, 2019). By gauging customers' genuine reactions and evaluations of frontline robots in hospitality and tourism service settings, this research seeks to establish how different categories of service robots, classified according to their level of human-likeness, might differentially affect consumer attitudes. Prior research into the influence of robots' human-likeness offers inconclusive and contradictory findings, suggesting both positive and negative effects (Rosenthal-von der Pütten and Krämer, 2014; Walters *et al.*, 2008). In general, a human-like appearance tends to evoke anthropomorphism, or attributions of human characteristics to non-human artifacts (McCartney and McCartney, 2020). By gauging customers' attitudes, as a

fundamental response to encountering service robots with varying levels of human-likeness, we seek to predict whether they will adopt approach or avoidance behavioral patterns (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993; Mitchell, 1986), which in turn imply acceptance or rejection of the technological innovation. With three categories of robots, classified according to their level of human-likeness, and a mixed-method approach involving qualitative and quantitative techniques, we seek a better understanding of customer's reactions, measured as their explicit and implicit attitudes toward robotic frontline agents.

Explicit attitudes reflect cognitive assessments, obtained when people think about and judge an object or agent according to an evaluative approach. They tend to be assessed with self-reported measures (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993). Implicit attitudes instead are unconscious and unintentional, driven directly by the stimulus without further deliberation by the person, who even may be unaware of these attitudes (De Houwer and Moors, 2007; Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2007). The manifestations, outcomes, and predictive capabilities of explicit and implicit attitudes in turn can differ. Explicit attitudes generally are more predictive of deliberative behaviors, whereas implicit attitudes signal spontaneous behaviors (Xu *et al.*, 2014). By gathering explicit attitudes, previous research relies on the assumption that people consciously process their experiences with and beliefs about robots (Belk, 2020; Gnambs and Appel, 2019), but implicit attitudes may be more relevant in frontline encounters, which often entail first impressions. Human-likeness, as a spontaneous cue that occurs during an initial encounter, also might evoke both direct responses (e.g., approach, avoidance) and encourage further cognitive processing. Despite these relevant influences, few studies include implicit attitudes toward robots (MacDorman *et al.*, 2009; Sanders *et al.*, 2016), and we know of none that pertain to hospitality and tourism or that analyze different categories of human-likeness.

To address these knowledge gaps, we turn to the uncanny valley (Mori, 1970) and construal level (Trope and Liberman, 2010) theories and develop propositions about whether

different robots, varying in their degree of human-likeness, lead to greater or lesser customer acceptance. In line with real-world practice, we distinguish three categories of robots currently being used in hospitality settings: mechanoids (low human-likeness), humanoids (medium human-likeness), and realistic robots (very human-like). Then we seek insights across three studies that rely on multiple methods, as detailed in Figure 1. That is, with a qualitative study with two focus groups, we learn about customers' overall attitudes toward different robots employed in hotels and restaurants, to establish knowledge about customers' perceptions of these innovations. Then with a quantitative approach, we measure individual explicit attitudes toward robots that represent the three categories of human-likeness in a carefully designed experiment. Finally, with another experiment, we assess customers' implicit (spontaneous, unconscious) attitudes toward the three categories of robots with three Implicit Association Tests (IAT) (Greenwald *et al.*, 1998). This instrument is widely used in psychology research to measure individual mental associations between target concepts and evaluative categories (Gawronski and De Houwer, 2014; Greenwald *et al.*, 1998), such as positive or negative valence associated with new types of social agents.

With this mixed-method approach, we can identify reasons customers accept or reject certain robots, according to their dual attitudes (Wilson *et al.*, 2000). Our research thus helps clarify whether the likelihood of positive or negative evaluations of specific robots is due to cognitive reasoning, reflected through explicit attitudes, or to internal, unconscious drivers. The insights offer a better means to measure the complex evaluative reactions that service robots may generate among customers, as consensual opinions (in qualitative studies) or at the individual level. As we demonstrate, this research field offers expansive opportunities for continued research. For practitioners, our study specifies positive and negative reactions that each robot design is likely to elicit among customers, such that they can design their introduction of such innovations better, to evoke more positive responses.

— INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE —

2. Literature review

2.1 Human-like robots in hospitality and tourism

Robots are “mechanical devices programmed to perform specific physical tasks without human intervention” (Belanche *et al.*, 2020b p. 205); service robots in particular perform useful tasks for humans, in ways that go beyond equipment involved in industrial automation (International Federation of Robotics, 2016). In hospitality and tourism settings, service robots provide luggage delivery, check-in, concierge, room service, wait staff, security, surveillance, and cleaning services (Revfine, 2020). Hotels such as Aloft, Yotel, and Flyzoo hope their uses of service robots will enhance frontline customer experiences (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a). The actual effects are uncertain though, as exemplified by ongoing debates pertaining to human–robot interactions and the effect of robots’ physical appearance on customers’ responses. As noted previously, when robots evoke perceptions of human-likeness, they also might spark anthropomorphism, such that customers attribute human-like features, traits, and behaviors to various objects, including virtual assistants and service robots (Aggarwal and McGill, 2007; Romero *et al.*, 2021). As a basic psychological process, based in inductive inference, anthropomorphism can facilitate social interactions, including human–robot interactions (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a; Christou *et al.*, 2020), because people tend to express positive view of objects with human-like features, reflecting the effects of human congruence schemas (Aggarwal and McGill, 2007) or familiarity (Epley *et al.*, 2007). Thus, more human-like robots might lead to positive attitudes and favorable responses (Pillai and Sivathanu, 2020; Tung and Au, 2018). However, another view predicts that customers develop more negative experiences when they interact with very human-like robots and prefer less human-like robots (McLean *et al.*, 2020; Mende *et al.*, 2019; Qiu *et al.*, 2020). Because the effect of robots’ human-likeness on consumer acceptance remains inconclusive (Rosenthal-von der Pütten and Krämer, 2014;

Walters *et al.*, 2008), further research is needed; we propose that further insights might be gleaned by testing customers' distinct reactions to different kinds of frontline robots. Therefore, we consider ascending degrees of human-likeness and classify service robots as mechanoid (low human-likeness), humanoid (medium human-likeness, with stylized, simplified human-like features), or realistic (high human-likeness, seem almost as fully human) (Walters *et al.*, 2008).

2.2 The uncanny valley and likeability

According to the uncanny valley theory (Mori, 1970), people express increasingly positive reactions to robots (e.g., likeability; Mori *et al.*, 2012) when these autonomous agents feature higher levels of human-likeness, but once they reach an extreme level of perfect humanness, people perceive the very human-like robots as unpleasant and eerie. Despite its long history, uncanny valley theory remains controversial, and efforts to confirm its effects have been inconclusive (Rosenthal-von der Pütten and Krämer, 2014; Walters *et al.*, 2008).

Social psychology also offers a relevant definition of likeability, as people's positive impressions of others, formed according to those others' visual and vocal behaviors (Clark and Rutter, 1985). A positive impression of likeability tends to prompt positive evaluations of the other entity (Robbins and DeNisi, 1994). When robots function, to some degree, as social actors (Nass *et al.*, 1996; van Doorn *et al.*, 2017), people likely judge them similarly, on the basis of their likeability. In turn, marketing research proposes that likeability relates to both cognitions and perceptions (Nguyen *et al.*, 2013), and these evaluative processes are precursors of attitudes (Bagozzi *et al.*, 1999).

2.3 Construal level theory (CLT)

A basic premise of construal level theory (CLT) (Trope and Liberman, 2003, 2010) is that people think more abstractly or concretely, depending on the degree of psychological distance they perceive from an object. If they think more concretely, they adopt low-level interpretations

and focus on practical details or secondary characteristics; if they think more abstractly, they focus on its essence, including general aspects of the object, and its long-term implications, such as whether it can aid their goal achievement (Trope and Liberman, 2010). In addition, CLT identifies four main dimensions of psychological distance (Trope and Liberman, 2010): temporal, spatial, social, and hypothetical. Fiedler (2007) argues for the relevance of experiential distance, because with more information gained through first- or second-hand experiences, people should display lower construal levels. In contrast, if information is scarce, such that the consequences of the event are difficult to predict, people likely adopt a higher construal level to develop their perceptions and inform their behaviors (Trope and Liberman, 2003).

Accordingly, we posit that when people interact with less human-like robots, which are similar to other machines that customers have experience with, they develop relatively concrete thoughts and adopt a low construal level, such that they pay attention to practical features and secondary details (e.g., tasks performed, benefits in the short term). However, realistic robots, which are more complex in appearance and less common, such that they appear more disruptive, might evoke a higher level of abstraction, such that people focus more on the essence of the activities these very human-like robots perform and their long-term implications.

Recent research that also applies CLT to study social robots confirms that customers' perceptions that robots possess sophisticated human abilities evoke higher construal levels, whereas robots with less human abilities prompt low construal levels (Kim and Duhachek, 2020). In addition to their abilities to perform tasks, robots that appear highly human-like might lead to higher construal levels, due to the disruptive nature of their distinctive physical appearance. Such high construal levels in turn might lead people to reject or avoid these robots, because their abstract thoughts include uncertainty about the long-term implications of the robots' widespread use. In short, CLT offers a framework for predicting why people might

develop more positive evaluations of low-construal, less human-like robots but more negative evaluations of realistic robots.

2.4 Attitudes

As fundamental constructs in social sciences (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993; Fazio, 1995), attitudes motivate human volitional behavior and affect various information processing stages. Eagly and Chaiken (1993, p. 1) define them as “a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor,” in which context a psychological tendency implies a state internal to the person, and the evaluation is manifest in approach or avoidance motivations. Accordingly, attitudes have critical relevance for social psychology, marketing, and communication research, as well as persuasion literature that often centers on the determinants of attitudinal changes (Mitchell, 1986). They also strongly affect intergroup relations (e.g., attitudes toward other groups, Oswald *et al.*, 2013) and new technology adoption (Davis, 1989). Combining all these research streams provides insights for predicting customers’ reactions to service robots, relative to their social behavior and technology acceptance, for which attitude represents a primary driver of users’ intentions and behaviors (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993; Fazio, 1995).

Therefore, by integrating the findings and theoretical insights provided in prior research, we develop predictions about customers’ attitudes toward service robots, which we test in our qualitative Study 1, conducted in hotels and restaurants. With focus groups, we gather in-depth insights into customers’ consensual attitudes and identify some reasons for their acceptance or rejection of service robots.

3. Study 1: Attitudes toward service robots

3.1 Do customers have favorable or unfavorable attitudes toward service robots?

The disruptive changes resulting from the introduction of robots to services spark controversy. From an optimistic perspective, their introduction should be beneficial, because

they can increase efficiency and enrich people's lives (Gnambs and Appel, 2019; Qiu *et al.*, 2020). Customers might be impressed by robots' appearance and skills (Qiu *et al.*, 2020), which leads to positive perceptions and attitudes (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a; McCartney and McCartney, 2020). Various hospitality and tourism studies identify customers' positive attitudes toward robots, which derive from their enhanced service experience (Tung and Au, 2018), enjoyment, or fun (Cha, 2020). Furthermore, previous evidence pertaining to optimal robot designs (Ivanov *et al.*, 2019) often suggests that a human-like appearance is more likely to cause positive perceptions and attitudes (Pillai and Sivathanu, 2020).

Yet as the immediacy of the technology increases, concerns and potential risks also become more prevalent. According to Gnambs and Appel (2019), Europeans' favorable perceptions toward robots have been decreasing, seemingly due to their concerns about the robots' ability to replace human employment (Kong *et al.*, 2021; Law *et al.*, 2020). These negative perceptions may be accentuated if the robots' physical appearance is similar to that of a human being (Wang *et al.*, 2015). Belk (2020) predicts that as machines become more human-like, people start worrying they can outsmart humans, in a power shift they regard as dangerous. In the hospitality and tourism sector, travelers feel often uncomfortable dealing with automated agents, which they perceive as impersonal, lifeless objects that dehumanize hotel services (Yu, 2020) or make tourism experiences frustrating and unpleasant (Kazandzhieva and Filipova, 2019; Qiu *et al.*, 2020). Considering the ambivalence that continues to mark extant literature, we pose a research question:

RQ1: What are hospitality and tourism customers' attitudes toward service robots that display different levels of human-likeness?

3.2 Focus groups

To explore customers' attitudes toward service robots with varying levels of human-likeness, we conducted four focus groups to gather participants' opinions and attitudes. These

insights provide critical input for the hypotheses we generate for our subsequent, quantitative studies (Fern, 1982). Focus group research is particularly effective for gaining a good understanding of the origin of complex behaviors and motivations (Morgan, 1996), because the group interactions encourage expressions of individual opinions and also provide consensual views of the focal topic.

The possibilities for incorporating service robots into hospitality and tourism contexts are broad, so for parsimony, we address two settings with clear implementation options: restaurants and hotels (Ivanov and Webster, 2019). To recruit the focus group participants, we posted a message requesting participation in “a study about service innovation in hotels and restaurants” on social media and posters on a university campus. The 30 people who agreed to participate were equally split by gender, and their ages ranged from 18 and 61 years. For each service setting (restaurants and hotels), we conducted two focus groups, divided by age (i.e., younger or older participants), which should help make them feel more comfortable and improve the flow of dialogue (Jarrett, 1993). The sessions lasted 90 minutes, and each group included 6–8 people who did not know each other previously, which limits interference (Fern, 1982). The sessions were moderated by a researcher with extensive previous experience with both focus groups and the subject matter. A research assistant took extensive notes, recounting both verbal and non-verbal communication by the participants, which complemented the audio recordings (obtained with participants’ consent).

During each session, participants viewed photographs of robots that varied in their human-likeness, performing service tasks in either hotels and restaurants, in separate rounds (see the Appendix). Before and after each round of observation, the participants provided their initial and consensus impressions, including their general opinion of each robot; its perceived advantages and disadvantages; any sense of attraction, threat, or rejection toward that robot; perceived cues for rapport building; previous experience with technological innovations in

services; preferences for dealing with robots versus people; and possible threats and opportunities.

3.3. Findings

3.3.1. Positive and negative attitudes toward robots

In an initial analysis of the focus group results, we coded the participants' comments according to whether they pertained to the robot's (1) appearance, (2) business application, or (3) other topics. Table 1 summarizes these results, along with some representative verbatim expressions. In turn, we can clarify that most positive opinions about robots relate to their capacity to attract curiosity/attention, as well as enhance customer experiences through their augmented skills (e.g., speaking hundreds of languages). Customers also have favorable perceptions of robots' cost-saving capacity and ability to release human employees from repetitive, hard work, so that they can offer personalized services. The focus group participants regard service robots as appropriate in transaction-based and low-cost establishments. But with regard to negative attitudes, we find that the participants perceive robots as cold and lacking understanding or flexibility to attend to customers' unique demands. They fear robot failures (and lack of failure recovery skills), prefer to avoid replacement of the human touch, and sense an overall threat to human employment in the medium and long term.

— INSERT TABLE 1 HERE —

3.3.2. Reactions to different degrees of human-likeness

The appearance of the service robot is a critical determinant of customers' first impressions. Highly realistic, human-like robots still represent a novelty, so they generate great interest and curiosity: "At the beginning, I would feel much curiosity for knowing what added value the robot can contribute to me and where its limits are" (Participant-17). Once past this initial, natural curiosity, most participants expressed a preference for relatively simple service robots that perform mechanical tasks, such as "to provide information and for room service, I

prefer a simpler robot and a kind of mechanoid” (P-23). Even if they express appreciation for the effort invested, customers also perceive robots that look just like people as intimidating, creepy, and disturbing, such that “I don’t like that the robot tries to imitate humans” (P-8). In turn, they generate distrust or suspicion of nefarious intentions (“I don't understand why they try to make it look so human; it’s as if they were trying to cheat us” [P-15]). In more detail, the participants prefer robots whose appearance matches their function, so for example, “the robots that transport suitcases should be very different of those that provide information” (P-29). Similarly, they believe robots and people should perform clearly differentiated tasks, which would reduce discomfort and distrust (“I don't like human-looking robots ... I'm not comfortable" [P-26]), as well as fears of replacing human workers (“a robot will never provide the same service as a specialized sommelier” [P-3]).

3.4. Discussion

These comments by focus group participants enrich our understanding of how customers perceive of and react to the presence of service robots in tourism and hospitality settings. With this qualitative evidence, we uncover both positive and negative evaluations of service robots. The consensual attitudes suggest that customers prefer less human-like robots that do not pretend to imitate human employees. We build on these insights to develop Study 2, in which we analyze individual, explicit attitudes toward service robots, using a quantitative, statistical comparison across the three categories of robots that vary in their level of human-likeness.

4. Study 2: Explicit attitudes toward service robots

4.1. Customers’ explicit attitudes and the role of human-likeness

Explicit attitudes reflect learned states; in human–robot interactions, they comprise the general thoughts and opinions people develop about robots by relying on their rationalized judgment of available cues (Sanders *et al.*, 2016). Because people engage in cognitive reasoning

and conscious thought to develop explicit attitudes, they can be measured with self-reported scales (Merrit *et al.*, 2013), as we detail in Section 4.2. To develop our hypothesis about how levels of human-likeness affect people's explicit attitudes, we rely on the focus group findings from Study 1, as well as relevant existing theory.

For example, the Computers Are Social Actors (CASA) paradigm describes human–computer encounters as parasocial interactions that adopt the social rules of human–human interactions (Nass *et al.*, 1995). Just as people judge other people on their appearance, perceptions of robots depend largely on their appearance (Walters *et al.*, 2008). If the robots offer human-like cues, people mindlessly apply a default human schema that prompts them to apply social rules to the interaction (Kim and Sundar, 2012). In the absence of a genuine robot identity, using physical appearances to infer personality or traits is a nearly automatic heuristic attribution (Belanche *et al.*, 2021; McCartney and McCartney, 2020; Walters *et al.*, 2008).

Yet there may be limits to these attributions, according to studies that detail how people's attitudes toward robots reflect their human-likeness (Walters *et al.*, 2008). For example, with an analysis of the faces of 80 real-world robots, Mathur and Reichling (2009) find that robots that appear nearly human prompt participants to rate them as more inappropriate. Customers also tend to evaluate services provided by highly human-like robots negatively (Kazandzhieva and Filipova, 2019), in line with the uncanny valley theory. That is, when robots are very human-like, people might respond negatively, such as with a lack of approval, avoidance, or rejection (Rosenthal-von der Pütten and Krämer, 2014). Such negative attitudes also might reflect concerns about human replacement, including the risk that the use of robots will lead to greater human unemployment (Kong *et al.*, 2021) in line with the AI-job replacement theory (Huang and Rust, 2018). In contrast, robots with less human-like appearances seem like less salient threats to human safety or resources, so people tend to feel more positively toward them (Złotowski *et al.*, 2017). In CLT terms, we predict that a very

human-like robot evokes higher construal levels, such that people focus on uncertain, abstract, long-term consequences of the introduction of this innovation (Kim and Duhachek, 2020).

Formally,

H1: Customers develop less favorable explicit attitudes toward service robots that appear more human-like.

4.2 Method

To gather customers' explicit attitudes about frontline robots, we asked them to evaluate 14 actual service robots with different levels of human-like appearances (Rosenthal-von der Püthen and Kramer, 2014): Actroid, Asuna, Atlas, Erica, Geminoid, Han, HRP-4, HRP-4C, K5, Kodomoroid, Toro, Robothespian, Savioke and Sofia. The 116 U.S. participants, recruited through a market research agency (64.7% women, 35.3% men; 13.8% aged 18–25, 37.0% aged 25–34, 34.5% aged 35–44, and 14.7% 45 years or older), read that they would be participating in a study of service innovations in hospitality, such that they would have to evaluate several frontline service robots that could be introduced in a hotel or restaurant. With a within-subject design, we asked these participants to evaluate the 14 robots sequentially, such that after viewing a photo of each robot, they answered a short online questionnaire that asked them to classify the robot and provide attitudes toward it. The robots were presented in random order, to avoid sequence effects; their names were not visible, to avoid any potential branding effects. The pictures also were as homogeneous as possible (e.g., size, quality). With ratings of 14 robots by 116 participants, we obtain 1,624 cases.

In the classification task, participants had to assign each robot to one of the three human-likeness categories (i.e., mechanoids, humanoids, and realistic robots); a description and picture of a prototypical robot belonging to each category were provided as examples (see the Appendix). The questionnaire continued with three items from Bhattacharjee (2000), adapted to our research context, that measure explicit attitudes on 7-point Likert scales: “I like this

robot,” “This robot is interesting to me,” and “I have a positive attitude toward this robot” (Cronbach’s alpha = .927). To limit common method bias, we applied procedural remedies, such as randomly counterbalancing the stimuli order, separating the measure with trivial questions, and promising complete anonymity (Podsakoff, 2003).

4.3 Results

The participants could distinguish easily among the three categories of robots, with a very high percentage of agreement (95%–100% correct assignments), with the notable exception of HRP4-C, which we thus discarded (i.e., 59.5% of participants categorize it as realistic and 39.6% as humanoid). On the basis of their responses, we classify K5 and Savioke robots as mechanoids (non-anthropomorphic, mechanical-like robots); Atlas, HRP-4, Toro, and Robothespian as humanoids (some anthropomorphic features); and Actroid, Asuna, Erika, Geminoid, Han, Kodomoroid, and Sophia as realistic (highly human appearance).

When we compare average attitudes across these three groups of robots, we find, in support of H1, that mechanoids earn the most positive attitude scores ($M = 4.468$), followed by humanoids ($M = 4.173$), and finally realistic robots ($M = 3.457$). With a within-subjects analysis of variance, we can confirm significant differences in attitude ($F = 36.558, p < .01$), and the differences for each pair of categories also are significant (Bonferroni tests, $p < .05$). Attitudes toward mechanoids ($t = 4.947, p < .01$) and humanoids ($t = 2.531, p < .05$) may appear slightly positive—greater than 4, the midpoint of the attitude scale—but attitudes toward realistic robots are significantly lower than 4 ($t = -9.897, p < .01$). In line with the descriptive statistics in Table 2, customers do not have very positive or negative explicit attitudes toward service robots, even if they have relatively less positive toward realistic ones (i.e., with highly human-like appearances).

— INSERT TABLE 2 HERE —

4.4. Discussion

Study 2 confirms that highly human-like, realistic robots evoke less favorable attitudes than less human-like robots (mechanoids or humanoids). In line with our theoretically derived hypothesis and focus group results, customers consciously reject robots with a high level of human-likeness. To gain more in-depth understanding of such attitudes, we also investigate customers' implicit attitudes with three separate IATs, to determine if they follow the same pattern.

5. Study 3: Implicit attitudes toward robots

5.1 Implicit attitudes and the IAT

Implicit attitudes are unintentional, unconscious, effortless, fast, and driven solely by the stimulus (De Houwer and Moors, 2007). To assess them, researchers often measure the speed with which people respond to the attitude object (e.g., robot) with a particular, evaluative representation (e.g., synonyms for "good"). According to an associative-propositional evaluation model (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2007), implicit attitudes operate solely by association in memory, which may reflect culture, the social environment, or education, rather than people's personal beliefs (Gawronski and De Houwer, 2014). To gauge them, IATs provide a valid, efficient method (Gawronski and De Houwer, 2014; Greenwald *et al.*, 1998). They have been applied to understand potentially sensitive topics such as racism, prejudice, and sexual behavior, as well as consumption preferences (Gawronski and De Houwer, 2014; Xu *et al.*, 2014).

With an IAT, it is possible to compare participants' automatic mental associations of two target concepts (e.g., robot vs. human) along an evaluative dimension (e.g., negative vs. positive), according to their reaction times in a combined categorization task, such that shorter reaction times indicate stronger associations between the target concept and positive or negative valence. Using alternating categories and response keys, an IAT is based on the premise that a response is easier if closely related categories share the same response key (De Houwer and

Moors, 2007). Thus, compared with self-reported measures of explicit attitudes, the IAT is more resistant to social desirability and self-presentation biases, such that it achieves greater reliability, better effect sizes, and strong discriminant validity (Gawronski and De Houwer, 2014; Xu *et al.*, 2014). Studies that have applied the IAT to marketing questions show, for example, that tests of customers' implicit attitudes toward brands (e.g., Pepsi, McDonald's) offer better predictive validity with regard to brand-related behaviors (Maison *et al.*, 2004) and more accurately capture the concealed influence of advertising (Venkatraman *et al.*, 2015), compared with self-reported measures. Hospitality and tourism literature also has adopted the IAT to evaluate destination images (Jang, 2016; Yang *et al.*, 2012). Accordingly, we use IATs to test people's implicit attitudes toward service robots, relative to human employees, as well as according to their level of human-likeness, as detailed in two additional hypotheses.

5.2 Hypotheses

5.2.1. Implicit attitudes toward human versus robot service providers. Most evidence suggests that people express more positive implicit attitudes toward humans than toward robots (Sanders *et al.*, 2016). For example, in a cross-cultural IAT, MacDorman *et al.* (2009) find that both U.S. and Japanese users indicate more negative implicit attitudes toward robots, so this implicit negativity appears common across cultures. Furthermore, from an anthropological perspective, monotheistic views assume human dominance and superiority over other creatures, because only humans possess mental and soul privilege (MacDorman *et al.*, 2009). But human-like robots challenge such deeply held views, which might evoke negative reactions (Belk, 2020). People also might evaluate robots more negatively because of their lack of emotion and empathy (MacDorman *et al.*, 2009). Thus, we hypothesize:

H2: Customers develop more favorable implicit attitudes toward service employees than toward service robots.

5.2.3. Implicit attitudes toward robots with varying levels of human-likeness.

According to findings from social psychology, people are more sensitive to physical variation among in-group members than out-group members (Judd and Park, 1988). If realistic robots enter the in-group of a human categorization (Kuchenbrandt *et al.*, 2013), consumers might be more sensitive to differences exhibited by highly anthropomorphic robots, compared with less anthropomorphic robots (McCartney and McCartney, 2020). In support of this prediction, previous research shows that people exhibit negative spontaneous reactions to service robots that are human-like (e.g., Mende *et al.*, 2019), especially if they are nearly human in appearance but imperfect in their human qualities (Mori *et al.*, 2012) or seem like a dead object come to life (i.e., the Frankenstein complex). These negative reactions typically reflect evolutionary mechanisms (MacDorman *et al.*, 2009; Wang *et al.*, 2015). In hospitality settings, frontline service robots may be evaluated negatively because they represent a new form that induces heightened human–object category uncertainty (Belanche *et al.*, 2020c; Strait *et al.*, 2017). From a CLT perspective, very human-like features should prompt higher construal levels, such that customers assess these realistic service robots in a more disruptive, abstract way (Kim and Duhachek, 2020), emphasizing their uncertainty about the implications of introducing robots to service provision (e.g., loss of human touch, challenge to humanness). In summary, we predict:

H3: Customers have less favorable implicit attitudes toward robots that appear more human-like.

5.3 Method

With the IAT, we seek to determine the implicit favorability or unfavorability that consumers express toward frontline robots or frontline human employees, across three conditions: mechanoids versus human employees, humanoids versus human employees, and realistic robots versus human employees. The design of the IATs followed recommendations from previous literature (Greenwald *et al.*, 2003), and they were conducted by BitBrain, a

neuroscience company that specializes in conducting such tests. The sample of 351 participants, recruited by a market research agency (55.6% women, 44.43% men; 3.1% aged 18–20, 20.0% aged 21–30, 40.7% aged 31–40, 21.4% aged 41–50, 14.8% 51 years or older), were randomly assigned to three groups in the between-subject design, such that each group performed a different IAT, and there were 107–122 participants per group.

Four separate images represent humans, mechanoids, humanoids, and realistic robots; then six positive (pleasant, likeable, familiar, fantastic, good, attractive) and six negative (unpleasant, annoying, threatening, scary, bad, disgusting) words represent evaluative valenced categories. Because an IAT provides an indirect measure based on response latency (Greenwald *et al.*, 1998), shorter response times indicate stronger implicit associations. Accordingly, the instructions asked participants to identify links as quickly as possible, so existing mental associations (e.g., humans/positive and robots/negative) should be identified more easily and quickly.

Each IAT consisted of seven blocks (Table 3), with five practice blocks (20 trials each) and two measurement blocks (40 trials each) in the fourth and seventh positions. The speed of responses in these two blocks are the input for the data analysis (Greenwald *et al.*, 2003). Socio-demographic information was collected after finishing the IAT.

— INSERT TABLE 3 HERE —

5.4 Results

The IAT score (or D-score) reflects how long it takes a respondent to sort items in the fourth block versus the seventh block (human-positive and robot-negative vs. robot-positive and human-negative), on average, so higher values indicate greater differences across the concept-evaluation groups. As the results in Table 4 indicate, the average response time is shorter for combinations of humans with positive adjectives (pictures of robots with negative adjectives), for all three IATs. Therefore, we find support for a stronger association of humans

with positive valence and a stronger association of robots with negative valence (Greenwald *et al.*, 2003), in support of H2.

In more detailed analyses of the D-scores (Greenwald *et al.*, 2003), we determine that the implicit positive preference for human service providers over both mechanoid ($D = .392$) and humanoid ($D = .384$) robots is small (score between .2 and .5). But we find a medium implicit preference for human employees over realistic robots ($D = .517$), with a D-score greater than .5 (Greenwald *et al.*, 2003). In combination, these results support H3.

— INSERT TABLE 4 HERE —

5.5 Discussion

By delving into customers' implicit attitudes toward service robots, Study 3 reveals that they evaluate robots more negatively than they do human employees, and this negative implicit bias persists across three categories of robots that vary in their degree of human-likeness. Yet in line with the findings of Studies 1 and 2, highly human-like, realistic robots generate even more negative implicit reactions than less human-like service robots.

6. General Discussion

Customer acceptance of service robots is critical for their successful introduction (Belanche *et al.*, 2020a; Kazandzhieva and Filipova, 2019; Loureiro *et al.*, 2020), so understanding what factors determine customers' reactions to robot agents is paramount; with a mixed-method design, we test whether and how different levels of human-likeness might influence customers' (explicit and implicit) attitudes, which in turn are likely to inform their behaviors and technological acceptance (Davis, 1989; Mitchell, 1986). Our qualitative study reveals that customers have both positive and negative consensual attitudes toward service robots in hospitality settings, in line with previous studies that identify both optimistic and pessimistic views in other contexts (Belk, 2020; Ivanov *et al.*, 2019). Robots raise people's curiosity and promise to enhance the customer experience by providing more precise, uniform, qualified, transaction-focused, consistent service. They also help companies save costs and

perform repetitive, difficult tasks. But customers find robots' coldness, potential failure, and lack of flexibility problematic, while also noting their threat to human employment, clear communication, or engaging service encounters (Qiu *et al.*, 2020). In turn, less human-like robots with basic features, that perform simple tasks, are preferred, whereas realistic robots are perceived as creepy, unnecessary, and more evidently imitating or trying to replace humans.

In line with these qualitative findings, Study 2 reveals that customers' explicit attitudes toward humanoid and mechanoid robots at the hospitality frontline are generally positive, but their explicit attitudes are less favorable with regard to realistic robots. They explicitly prefer less human-like robots (mechanoids or humanoids) and offer clear, negative evaluations of robots that look very human-like. By also obtaining implicit attitudes, with Study 3 we add two further findings. First, customers have an implicit preference for human employees over robots in hotels and restaurants, matching their explicit attitudes. Second, their implicit attitudes are particularly negative in reaction to highly human-like robots. Compared with the relatively minimal negative unconscious reaction toward mechanoids and humanoids, their negative responses are strong when customers encounter realistic robots.

6.1 Theoretical implications

Combining the findings from all three of our studies, we can establish several theoretical contributions. As noted, we find support for the existence of the uncanny valley effect, using both explicit and implicit measures (Mori, 1970). Robots that look more mechanical or have just limited human-likeness are accepted nearly as well as human employees. In these interactions, customers acknowledge the functional value of the robots, especially for performing simple tasks and contributing to the business and society, even if they still worry about dehumanized social interactions in hotels and restaurants. But highly human-like robots evoke negative explicit and implicit attitudes, such that customers appear to experience,

consciously and unconsciously, negative reactions to robots that try to imitate human features, seemingly because of the threat of negative implications for humankind.

These negative attitudes may stem from the higher-level construals that realistic robots evoke, due to the uncertainty of the long-term consequences they represent, were such robots to be incorporated into people's daily lives. We recommend integrating CLT (Trope and Liberman, 2010) as a framework for understanding uncanny valley effects in service contexts. As we show, customers perceive low- or medium human-like robots as more practical, task-concrete, and short-term-oriented instruments (low construal level), whereas highly human-like robots prompt them to think in more abstract and distant ways that make the uncertain consequences of robot introductions more salient. At this high construal level, people sense threats, consciously and unconsciously, perhaps due to a general fear that robots might evade human control and begin to outsmart or overpower us (Belk, 2020; Loureiro *et al.*, 2020).

Our findings also confirm previous predictions and explain some relevant influences. For example, customers' preferences for less human-like robots (low construal level) offers insight into why they also are more comfortable with robots assisting them in tasks that require concrete, physical, or manual labor (e.g., luggage handler) rather than cognitive or emotional skills (e.g., receptionist, manager) (Gnambs and Appel, 2019). Other studies (e.g., Christou *et al.*, 2020; Kim and Sundar, 2012) predict that customers apply heuristics on the basis of robot's physical appearance, such that this first impression strongly influences customers' favorable or unfavorable evaluations of these frontline agents, which resonates with our findings. Finally, we offer a rationale for the evidence in previous studies that people are reluctant to engage with highly human-like robots (high construct level) for certain activities, such as living in the same house or watching a movie performed by robots (Oyedele *et al.*, 2007).

With regard to customers' implicit attitudes in particular, we provide the first assessment of three groups of robots, classified by their level of human-likeness, that are widely employed

in hospitality settings. Their negative reactions to all three types of robots corroborates some general findings (e.g., MacDorman *et al.* 2009; Sanders *et al.*, 2016) and highlights the need to find ways to overcome consumers' initial spontaneous rejections of robots. As a novel finding, we clarify that implicit attitudes are particularly negative toward highly human-like robots, in line with the uncanny valley effect.

Finally, the CLT-based theoretical framework offers a valuable perspective for addressing these questions. For example, if robot designers or service providers could reduce the psychological distance between users and robots, they might encourage customers to replace their high construal, abstract thinking with more concrete, low construal levels (e.g., practical benefits). Emphasizing more practical functions of robots could prompt customers to focus on the present, immediate benefits they can derive. Similarly, more frequent interactions with robots might reduce customers' informative and experiential distances, as suggested by CLT. Such suppositions of course require further confirmation.

6.2 Managerial implications

Because customers' perceptions of service robots' appearance determine their favorable or unfavorable attitudes, they also likely affect the customer experience (Ivanov and Webster, 2019; Tung and Au, 2018). Robot designers might be driven to create the most realistic robots they can, but our research suggests that these are not the robots that service providers should introduce at their frontline. Rather, they should avoid realistic robots, which can prompt both negative cognitive evaluations (explicit negative attitude) and spontaneous rejection (implicit negative attitude) among customers. That is, customers are likely to intentionally and unintentionally reject very human-like robots in service encounters.

Considering that customers do not want robots that try to imitate or replace humans, practitioners also need to find alternative ways to provide services. In this regard, our research reveals that both mechanoids and humanoids are welcomed by customers. Mechanoids appear

particularly useful for performing simple, repetitive, high-effort, low-interaction tasks (e.g., luggage transport, room service, bussing tables), and humanoid robots can be used in more interactive encounters (e.g., reception desk, welcome) or to support human employees by offering specific skills (e.g., translation into different languages). Our qualitative analyses offer deep insights for how practitioners should introduce service robots to leverage customers' keen awareness of the potential benefits of using robots in hospitality and tourism.

Finally, practitioners should keep in mind that customers regard robots as a type of dehumanized service, which is particularly concerning in the hospitality and tourism sector (Yu, 2020), where customer experience and satisfaction are crucial. Thus, managers should introduce robots carefully and in a limited capacity, such as to perform specific tasks at a few interaction points, especially those that only require transaction-based encounters. Beyond tasks that require mechanical or analytical intelligence, robots increasingly can exhibit empathetic or emotional skills (Huang and Rust, 2018), as is evident among the latest generations of voice assistants and chatbots too (Ashfaq *et al.*, 2020; Loureiro *et al.*, 2021). But according to our findings, the human touch provided by frontline employees continues to be highly relevant to customers.

6.3 Limitations and further research lines

In addressing individual attitudes toward different kinds of service robots, some of our measures and assessment may have treated attitude as an affective rather than an evaluative concept (Bagozzi *et al.*, 1999). An attitude is a judgment or summary evaluation of an object (Fazio, 1995); an emotion is “a mental state of readiness that arises from cognitive appraisals of events or thoughts; has a phenomenological tone; is accompanied by physiological processes; is often expressed physically; and may result in specific actions to or cope with the emotion” (Bagozzi *et al.*, 1999, p.184). Thus, attitude and emotions entail different definitions, etiology, measures, and influences on decisions and behavior (e.g., Perugini and Bagozzi,

2001). We recommend further research that explicitly identifies the unique effects of robot human-likeness on attitudes versus emotions, and then the resulting, distinct influences on customer decisions and behaviors. In this effort, our qualitative study could provide a relevant foundation for understanding customers' emotions in relation to robots.

Although our mixed-method approach offers strong internal validity and addresses both explicit and implicit attitudes, continued efforts might pursue greater external validity, such as with field studies. Customers' reactions to service robots in actual establishments arguably might be even more intense, in that direct experiences with disruptive technologies can strongly trigger both explicit and implicit attitudes. Moreover, we acknowledge some criticisms of the IAT, namely, that the results reflect salient asymmetries between categories or prevalent stereotypes in society, not necessarily individual beliefs (Arkes and Tetlock, 2004). In relation to social and racial stereotypes, Oswald *et al.* (2013) argue that the IAT offers low utility as a predictor of behavior. Thus continued research, using alternative methodologies, is necessary to clarify the reasons for negative reactions, particularly implicit ones, to highly human-like robots (Gnambs and Appel, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2015).

Finally, as a timely option for further research, we suggest investigations of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on robot acceptance. The use of robots as allies to limit the spread of the virus may increase customers' positive attitudes toward frontline robots (González-Jiménez, 2020), even to the extent that customers might grow to prefer robot over human service providers in hospitality settings (Jiang and Wen, 2020). Additional studies might test how people's attitudes toward robots evolve in the post-COVID-19 era, as well as define marketing strategies that can contribute to shaping such attitudes.

References

- Aggarwal, P., and McGill, A. L. (2007), "Is that car smiling at me? Schema congruity as a basis for evaluating anthropomorphized products", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 34 No. 4, pp.468-479.
- Arkes, H. R., and Tetlock, P. E. (2004), "Attributions of implicit prejudice, or "would Jesse Jackson 'Fail' the Implicit Association Test?"". *Psychological Inquiry*, Vol. 15 No. 4, pp.257-278.
- Ashfaq, M., Yun, J., Yu, Sh., and Loureiro, S. M. C. (2020), "I, Chatbot: Modeling the Determinants of Users' Satisfaction and Continuance Intention of Text-based Conversational Agents", *Telematics and Informatics*, Vol. 54 No. 3, p.101473
- Bagozzi, R. P., Gopinath, M., and Nyer, P. U. (1999), "The role of emotions in marketing", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 27 No. 2, pp.184-206.
- Belanche, D., Casaló, L. V., and Flavián, C. (2020a), "Frontline robots in tourism and hospitality: service enhancement or cost reduction?", *Electronic Markets*, Vol. 66 No. 2, pp.1-16.
- Belanche, D., Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., and Schepers, J. (2020b), "Service robot implementation: a theoretical framework and research agenda", *The Service Industries Journal*, Vol. 40 No. 3-4, pp.203-225.
- Belanche, D., Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., and Schepers, J. (2020c), "Robots or frontline employees? Exploring customers' attributions of responsibility and stability after service failure or success", *Journal of Service Management*, Vol. 31 No. 2, pp.267-289.
- Belanche, D., Casalo, L. V., Flavián, C., and Schepers, J. (2021), "Examining the effects of robots' physical appearance, warmth, and competence in frontline services: The Humanness-Value-Loyalty model", *Psychology & Marketing*, In press, Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/mar.21532>
- Belk, R. (2020), "Ethical issues in service robotics and artificial intelligence", *The Service Industries Journal*, Vol. 43 No. 3, pp.1-17.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2000), "Acceptance of e-commerce services: the case of electronic brokerages", *IEEE Transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics-Part A: Systems and humans*, Vol. 30 No. 4, pp.411-420.

- Cha, S.S. (2020), "Customers' intention to use robot-serviced restaurants in Korea: relationship of coolness and MCI factors", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 9, pp.2947-2968.
- Christou, P., Simillidou, A. and Stylianou, M.C. (2020), "Tourists' perceptions regarding the use of anthropomorphic robots in tourism and hospitality", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 11, pp. 3665-3683.
- Clark, N., and Rutter, D. (1985), "Social categorization, visual cues and social judgments", *European Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol.15 No. 1, pp.105-119.
- Davis, F. D. (1989), "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol.13 No.3, pp.319-340.
- De Houwer, J., and Moors, A. (2007), "How to define and examine the implicitness of implicit measures", *Implicit measures of attitudes: Procedures and controversies*, The Guilford Press, New York London, pp.179-194.
- Eagly, A. H., and Chaiken, S. (1993), "*The psychology of attitudes*", Harcourt brace Jovanovich college publishers, New York, NY.
- Epley, N., Waytz, A., and Cacioppo, J. T. (2007), "On seeing human: a three-factor theory of anthropomorphism", *Psychological review*, Vol. 114 No. 4, p.864.
- Fazio, R. H. (1995), "Attitudes as object-evaluation associations: determinants, consequences, and correlates of attitude accessibility," in *Attitude strength: Antecedents and consequences*, R. E. Petty and J. A. Krosnick eds., Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc., pp.247-282.
- Fern, E. F. (1982), "The use of focus groups for idea generation: the effects of group size, acquaintanceship, and moderator on response quantity and quality", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp.1-13.
- Fiedler, K. (2007), "Construal level theory as an integrative framework for behavioral decision-making research and consumer psychology", *Journal of Consumer Psychology*. Vol. 17 No. 2, pp.101–106.
- Gawronski, B., and Bodenhausen, G. V. (2007), "Unraveling the processes underlying evaluation: Attitudes from the perspective of the APE model", *Social Cognition*, Vol. 25 No. 5, pp.687-717.

- Gawronski, B., and De Houwer, J. (2014), Implicit measures in social and personality psychology. In H. T. Reis & C. M. Judd (Eds.), *Handbook of research methods in social and personality psychology*, Cambridge University Press, p. 283–310.
- Gnambs, T., and Appel, M. (2019), “Are robots becoming unpopular? Changes in attitudes towards autonomous robotic systems in Europe”, *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 93, pp.53-61.
- González-Jiménez, H. (2020), “Robots in daily life: A post COVID-19 perspective”, In Bunkanwanicha, P., Coeurderoy, R., and Ben Slimane, S. Editor (Ed.), *Managing a Post-Covid-19 Era*, ESCP Impact Paper No. 2020-62-EN, available at: <https://academ.escpeurope.eu/pub/IP%202020-62-EN.pdf> (accessed 20 February 2021).
- Greenwald, A. G., McGhee, D. E. and Schwartz, J. L. K. (1998), “Measuring individual differences in implicit cognition: the implicit association test,” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 74 No. 6, pp.1464-1480.
- Greenwald, A. G., Nosek, B. A. and Banaji, M. R. (2003), “Understanding and using the implicit association test: I. An improved scoring algorithm,” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 85 No. 2, pp.197-216.
- Huang, M. H. and Rust, R. T. (2018), “Artificial intelligence in service,” *Journal of Service Research*, Vol. 21 No. 2, pp.155-172.
- International Federation of Robotics. (2016). Executive Summary World Robotics 2016 Service Robots. Available at: https://ifr.org/downloads/press/02_2016/Executive_Summary_Service_Robots_2016.pdf (accessed 20 March 2021).
- Ivanov, S., Gretzel, U., Berezina, K., Sigala, M., and Webster, C. (2019), “Progress on robotics in hospitality and tourism: a review of the literature”, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp.489–521.
- Ivanov, S. and Webster, C. (2019), “Conceptual Framework of the Use of Robots, Artificial Intelligence and Service Automation in Travel, Tourism, and Hospitality Companies”, Ivanov, S. and Webster, C. (Ed.) *Robots, Artificial Intelligence, and Service Automation in Travel, Tourism and Hospitality*, Emerald Publishing Limited, pp.7-37.
- Jang, D. (2016), “Explicit and implicit attitudes and attitude changes toward tourism destinations: Las Vegas, USA, versus Jeongseon, South Korea”, *International Journal of Tourism Research*, Vol. 18 No. 5, pp.417-422.

- Jarrett, R. (1993), "Focus Group Interviewing with Low-Income Minority Populations: A Research Experience", in D. Morgan (ed.) *Successful Focus Groups: Advancing the State of the Art*, Newbury Park, CA: Sage, pp.184 –201.
- Jiang, Y., and Wen, J. (2020), "Effects of COVID-19 on hotel marketing and management: a perspective article", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 8, pp. 2563-2573
- Judd, C. M., and Park, B. (1988), "Out-group homogeneity: Judgments of variability at the individual and group levels," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 54 No. 5, pp. 778-788.
- Kazandzhieva, V., and Filipova, H. (2019), "Customer attitudes toward robots in travel, tourism, and hospitality: A conceptual framework". In *Robots, Artificial Intelligence, and Service Automation in Travel, Tourism and Hospitality*, Emerald Publishing Limited, UK, pp. 79-92
- Kim, T. W., and Duhachek, A. (2020), "Artificial Intelligence and persuasion: a construal-level account", *Psychological Science*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp.363-380.
- Kim, Y., and Sundar, S. S. (2012), "Anthropomorphism of computers: Is it mindful or mindless?", *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 28 No. 1, pp.241-250.
- Kong, H., Yuan, Y., Baruch, Y., Bu, N., Jiang, X. and Wang, K. (2021), "Influences of artificial intelligence (AI) awareness on career competency and job burnout", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 717-734.
- Kuchenbrandt, D., Eyssel, F., Bobinger, S., and Neufeld, M. (2013), "When a robot's group membership matters", *International Journal of Social Robotics*, Vol. 5 No. 3, pp.409-417.
- Law, R., Leung, D. and Chan, I.C.C. (2020), "Progression and development of information and communication technology research in hospitality and tourism: A state-of-the-art review", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 2, pp. 511-534.
- Loureiro, S. M. C., Guerreiro, J., and Tussyadiah, I. (2020), "Artificial intelligence in business: State of the art and future research agenda", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 129 No. 2, pp. 911-926

- Loureiro, S. M. C., Japutra, A., Molinillo, S., and Bilro, R. G. (2021), "Stand by me: analyzing the tourist-intelligent voice assistant relationship quality", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Article in press.
- MacDorman, K. F., Vasudevan, S. K., and Ho, C. C. (2009), "Does Japan really have robot mania? Comparing attitudes by implicit and explicit measures", *AI & Society*, Vol. 23 No. 4, pp.485-510.
- Maison, D., Greenwald, A. G. and Bruin, R. H. (2004), "Predictive validity of the Implicit Association Test in studies of brands, consumer attitudes, and behavior," *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 14 No. 4, pp.405-415.
- Mariani, M. M., and Borghi, M. (2021), "Customers' evaluation of mechanical artificial intelligence in hospitality services: a study using online reviews analytics", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, SSN 0959-6119 (In Press).
- Mathur, M. B., and Reichling, D. B. (2009), "An uncanny game of trust: social trustworthiness of robots inferred from subtle anthropomorphic facial cues", *4th ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction (HRI)*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, pp. 313-314.
- McCartney, G. and McCartney, A. (2020), "Rise of the machines: towards a conceptual service-robot research framework for the hospitality and tourism industry", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 12, pp. 3835-3851.
- McLean, G., Osei-Frimpong, K., Wilson, A. and Pitardi, V. (2020), "How live chat assistants drive travel consumers' attitudes, trust and purchase intentions: The role of human touch", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 5, pp.1795-1812.
- Mende, M., Scott, M. L., van Doorn, J., Grewal, D., and Shanks, I. (2019) "Service robots rising: How humanoid robots influence service experiences and elicit compensatory consumer responses", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 56 No. 4, pp.535-556.
- Merritt, S. M., Heimbaugh, H., LaChapell, J., and Lee, D. (2013), "I trust it, but I don't know why: Effects of implicit attitudes toward automation on trust in an automated system", *Human factors*, Vol. 55 No. 3, pp.520-534.

- Mitchell, A. A. (1986), "The effect of verbal and visual components of advertisements on brand attitudes and attitude toward the advertisement", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp.12-24.
- Morgan, D. L. (1996), "Focus groups", *Annual Review of Sociology*, Vol. 22 No. 1, pp.129-152.
- Mori, M. (1970), "The uncanny valley," *Energy*, Vol. 7 No. 4, pp.33–35.
- Mori, M., MacDorman, K. F., and Kageki, N. (2012), "The uncanny valley [from the field]", *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp.98-100.
- Nass, C., Moon, Y., Fogg, B. J., Reeves, B., and Dryer, C. (1995), "Can computer personalities be human personalities?", *In Conference companion on Human factors in computing systems*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, pp. 228-229.
- Nguyen, B., Melewar, T. C., and Chen, J. (2013), "A framework of brand likeability: an exploratory study of likeability in firm-level brands", *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 368-390.
- Oswald, F. L., Mitchell, G., Blanton, H., Jaccard, J., and Tetlock, P. E. (2013), "Predicting ethnic and racial discrimination: a meta-analysis of IAT criterion studies", *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 105 No. 2, pp.171.
- Oyedele, A., Hong, S., and Minor, M. S. (2007), "Contextual factors in the appearance of consumer robots: exploratory assessment of perceived anxiety toward human-like consumer robots", *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, Vol. 10 No. 5, pp.624-632.
- Perugini, M., and Bagozzi, R. P. (2001), "The role of desires and anticipated emotions in goal-directed behaviours: Broadening and deepening the theory of planned behavior", *British Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol. 40 No. 1, pp.79-98.
- Pillai, R. and Sivathanu, B. (2020), "Adoption of AI-based chatbots for hospitality and tourism", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 10, pp.3199-3226.
- Podsakoff, N. P. (2003), "Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88 No. 5, pp. 879.

- Qiu, H., Li, M., Shu, B., and Bai, B. (2020), "Enhancing hospitality experience with service robots: The mediating role of rapport building", *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, Vol. 29 No. 3, pp.247-268.
- Revfine (2020), "8 Examples of Robots Being Used in the Hospitality Industry", Available at: <https://www.revfine.com/robots-hospitality-industry/> (accessed 28 October 2020)
- Robbins, T., and DeNisi, A. (1994), "A closer look at interpersonal affect as a distinct influence on cognitive processing in performance evaluations". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 79 No. 3, pp.341-353.
- Romero, J., Ruiz-Equihua, D., Loureiro, S. M. C., and Casaló, L. V. (2021). "Smart Speaker Recommendations: Impact of Gender Congruence and Amount of Information on Users' Engagement and Choice", *Frontier in Psychology*, Vol. 12 No. 2, pp. 1037.
- Rosenthal-Von Der Pütten, A. M., and Krämer, N. C. (2014), "How design characteristics of robots determine evaluation and uncanny valley related responses", *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 36 No.1, pp.422-439.
- Sanders, T. L., Schafer, K. E., Volante, W., Reardon, A., and Hancock, P. A. (2016), "Implicit attitudes toward robots", *In Proceedings of the human factors and ergonomics society annual meeting*, Los Angeles, CA, SAGE Publications, Vol. 60 No. 1, pp.1746-1749.
- Strait, M. K., Floerke, V. A., Ju, W., Maddox, K., Remedios, J. D., Jung, M. F., and Urry, H. L. (2017), "Understanding the uncanny: both atypical features and category ambiguity provoke aversion toward humanlike robots", *Frontiers in Psychology*, Vol. 8 No. 4 p.1366.
- Trope, Y., and Liberman, N. (2003), "Temporal construal", *Psychological Review*, Vol. 110 No. 3, pp.403.
- Trope, Y., and Liberman, N. (2010), "Construal-level theory of psychological distance", *Psychological Review*, Vol. 117 No. 2, pp.440.
- Tung, V.W.S. and Au, N. (2018), "Exploring customer experiences with robotics in hospitality", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 30 No. 7, pp.2680-2697.
- Van Doorn, J., Mende, M., Noble, S. M., Hulland, J., Ostrom, A. L., Grewal, D., et al. (2017), "Domo arigato Mr. Roboto: emergence of automated social presence in organizational

- frontlines and customers' service experiences", *Journal of Service Research*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp.43–58.
- Venkatraman, V., Dimoka, A., Pavlou, P. A., Vo, K., Hampton, W., Bollinger, B., Hersfield, H. E. Ishihara, M. and Winer, R. S. (2015), "Predicting advertising success beyond traditional measures: New insights from neurophysiological methods and market response modeling," *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 52 No. 4, pp.436-452.
- Walters, M. L., Syrdal, D. S., Dautenhahn, K., Te Boekhorst, R., and Koay, K. L. (2008), "Avoiding the uncanny valley: robot appearance, personality and consistency of behavior in an attention-seeking home scenario for a robot companion", *Autonomous Robots*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp.159-178.
- Wang, S., Lilienfeld, S. O., and Rochat, P. (2015), "The uncanny valley: Existence and explanations", *Review of General Psychology*, Vol. 19 No. 4, pp.393-407.
- Wilson, T. D., Lindsey, S., and Schooler, T. Y. (2000), "A model of dual attitudes", *Psychological Review*, Vol. 107 No. 1, p.101.
- Xu, K., Nosek, B., and Greenwald, A. (2014), "Data from the race implicit association test on the project implicit demo website", *Journal of Open Psychology Data*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 1-3.
- Xu, S., Stienmetz, J. and Ashton, M. (2020), "How will service robots redefine leadership in hotel management? A Delphi approach", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 32 No. 6, pp. 2217-2237.
- Yang, J., He, J. and Gu, Y. (2012), "The implicit measurement of destination image: The application of Implicit Association Tests" *Tourism Management*, Vol. 33 No.1, pp.50-52.
- Yu, C. E. (2020), "Humanlike robots as employees in the hotel industry: Thematic content analysis of online reviews", *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp.22-38.
- Złotowski, J., Yogeewaran, K., and Bartneck, C. (2017), "Can we control it? Autonomous robots threaten human identity, uniqueness, safety, and resources", *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, Vol. 100 No.1, pp.48-54.

Figure 1. Overview of Studies

Table 1. Qualitative study findings: Positive and negative attitudes toward robots

Concept	Description	Verbatim Statements
Positive Attitudes		
Curiosity attraction	Robots can attract attention at specific events or among certain clients, such as kids or those who are passionate about new technologies and their future applications	<i>“it would be great if, when you arrive at the hotel, you were welcomed by a robot and could check in, talk to it” (P-27)</i>
Customer experience enhancement	Robots carry out some tasks with greater precision, uniformity, and quality; avoid service interruptions (e.g., 24/7); and can support employees by leveraging their artificial intelligence (e.g., foreign language skills, physical capacities)	<i>“robots would not make mistakes... preparing dishes for people with food intolerances or allergies” (P-5)</i> <i>“there are hundreds of languages spoken in the world and very few people speak sign language” (P-11)</i>
Human release from repetitive or hard work to focus on personalized attention	Robots can release employees from carrying out mechanical, repetitive, or unpleasant tasks (e.g., washing and stacking dishes), those that require greater physical effort or coordination of various sources of information. In turn, human are free to carry out other tasks, such as providing personalized attention.	<i>“robots could take the luggage from the reception to the rooms” (P-30)</i> <i>“the services that require less personalized treatment ... could be provided by a robot releasing the employee ...” (P-25)</i>
Cost saving	Companies can save costs and offer more competitive services by reducing the number of personnel needed or increasing productivity by using robots to perform specific tasks	<i>“could distribute the food with drones, ... avoiding traffic jams and salary increases for the delivery staff” (P-12)</i>
Appropriate for transaction-based and low price services	The use of robots is more suitable in transactional and low price service settings, rather than relational and high price services. Robots are appreciated when they provide quicker service if speed is key (e.g., fast food) but not as much in traditional hotels or restaurants	<i>“in McDonalds or other fast food places you don't care about that, ... you look for speed, ...” (P-22)</i> <i>“in roadside hotels they can be useful to extend the reception hours” (P-14)</i> <i>“in this type of restaurant you seek to socialize, for that you must be welcomed by a person.” (P-10)</i>
Negative Attitudes		

Lack of personal touch	Robots are impersonal and lack a common social background. Customers prefer humans over robot for certain services. Robots are perceived as not empathetic; if customers are having a bad day, they appreciate friendly (human) service.	<i>“is not the same as an expert sommelier describing the characteristics of a good wine and how to pair it... with the dishes,... imagine that a machine gives you that information with a metallic tone” (P-18).</i>
Lack of flexibility and understanding	Robots lack flexibility for managing customer requests, because they apply clear, precise, predetermined criteria. Some customer do not feel completely understood when dealing with robots, which is very frustrating for them.	<i>“A quality service requires knowing how to distinguish ... between some situations and others” (P-6) “I hate talking to a machine that doesn't understand me, nor put itself in my place...” (P-28)</i>
Robot failure	Robots can malfunction; resolving these failures may require the presence of human employees. This problem could be greater, depending on the severity of the failure and the time it takes for the company to provide a satisfactory response. Users do not feel comfortable addressing problems with a robot.	<i>“people are more tactful and are more affective... they are able to understand how I feel and what I can wish for in every moment” (P-7). “robots are very impersonal; it's like talking to a cell phone operator”(P-28)</i>
Robots substituting for humans	Customers do not like the idea of replacing employees completely and instead believe the robots should collaborate with humans to offer better service (e.g., work with someone with a disability, speak in many languages)	<i>“Robots can replace workers and that would be harmful for all of us” (P-24) “they could be helpful collaborating with humans (P-3)”</i>
Robots reducing human employment	The elimination of jobs related to the introduction of robots generates very strong negative attitudes because customers realize that many workers may lose their jobs. Customers also fear that due to their improving skills, robots may be extended to other sectors, putting their own work at risk.	<i>“if the robots are faster and more accurate, are tireless, have no vacation, or ask for salary increases, all the waiters will be fired” (P-5) “It makes my hair stand on end thinking about how much robots could take over our work” (P-16)</i>

Table 2. Study 2 results: Within-group differences in explicit attitudes

Robot groups	Mechanoids		Humanoids		Realistic Robots	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Explicit Attitude	4.468	1.067	4.173	0.950	3.470	1.051

Table 3. Study 3 procedure: Sequence of IAT blocks

Block	Function	Items assigned to “E”-Key response	Items assigned to “I”-Key response
1	Practice	Pictures of Humans	Pictures of Robots
2	Practice	Positive adjectives	Negative adjectives
3	Practice	Pictures of Humans + Positive adjectives	Pictures of Robots + Negative adjectives
4	Measure	Pictures of Humans + Positive adjectives	Pictures of Robots + Negative adjectives
5	Practice	Negative adjectives	Positive adjectives
6	Practice	Pictures of Humans + Negative adjectives	Pictures of Robots + Positive adjectives
7	Measure	Pictures of Humans + Negative adjectives	Pictures of Robots + Positive adjectives

Table 4. Study 3 results

IAT	N	Average response (seconds) Block 4 (human-positive vs. robot-negative)	Average response (seconds) Block 7 (human-negative vs. robot-positive)	D-Score
Humans vs. Mechanoids	107	.725	.836	.392
Humans vs. Humanoids	122	.732	.882	.384
Humans vs. Realistic	122	.809	1.002	.517

Appendix.

Pictures of mechanoid, humanoid, and realistic robots

Mechanoid

Humanoid

Realistic

